

Hydrogen evolution reaction at different pH of 2D MoS₂ prepared via liquid-phase exfoliation

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ABSTRACT

This study reports the successful preparation of exfoliated MoS₂ structures from the bulk powder using liquid-phase exfoliation (LPE), leading to a significant improvement in electrochemical properties for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) without modification of the flakes. Utilizing green solvent systems, acetone/water and butanol/ethanol, the study highlights the importance of solvent selection and optimization for achieving efficient exfoliation and catalytic performance. The acetone/water system, with an optimal ratio of 45/55, produced uniform 2D MoS₂ flakes with enhanced catalytic performance, especially in acidic media, where the samples exhibited high current densities and efficient charge transfer. After 2000 HER cycles, this system achieved an overpotential of 365 mV at -10 mA·cm⁻², demonstrating both performance and stability improvements. Although less efficient overall, the butanol/ethanol system showed promising results in alkaline conditions with best ratio of 30/70. These findings confirm the importance of solvent selection in MoS₂ exfoliation and highlight the potential of this material as a catalyst for hydrogen production. Further optimization of solvent ratios could enhance the catalytic efficiency of MoS₂ for energy applications and scalability for industrial applications.

1. Introduction

Two-dimensional (2D) materials, especially transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs), have received considerable attention in recent years. This is due to their unique physical and chemical properties, which often contrast with those of their bulk counterparts [1,2]. In general, TMDs have the formula MX₂, where M represents a transition metal (e.g. molybdenum, tungsten...) and X is a chalcogen (e.g. sulfur, selenium...) [3]. The layered structures of TMDs are held together by weak van der Waals interactions, which allows for easy exfoliation of individual nanolayers [4,5]. These nanolayers exhibit unique properties, including an indirect to direct bandgap transition [6], enhanced photoluminescence [7–9], and excellent catalytic performance [10,11]. One type of TMDs is MoS₂, which has shown significant potential in applications ranging from electronics [12,13] and energy storage [14–16] to catalysis [10,11].

In catalytic hydrogen evolution (HER), MoS₂ nanosheets outperform their bulk counterparts [17–19]. In particular, due to the larger surface

area, improved charge transport and a larger number of active edge sites [20,21]. Liquid phase exfoliation (LPE) appears to be a practical and scalable method for the production of MoS₂ nanosheets. This technique uses ultrasonication, which, in combination with a suitable solvent, delaminates the bulk TMDs [22,23]. The choice of solvent plays a crucial role, as it affects not only the exfoliation efficiency and the stability of the nanosheets, but also the environmental sustainability of the process in case of green solvents [24–26].

Green solvents such as acetone, ethanol, and butanol have gained attention for their environmental compatibility and effective performance in LPE processes [27]. Acetone, known for its affordability, low toxicity, and high volatility, supports rapid exfoliation while leaving minimal solvent residue, making it suitable for large-scale production [28,29]. Ethanol, a renewable solvent derived from biomass, excels in stabilizing exfoliated nanosheets due to its favorable surface energy properties and minimal environmental impact [30,31]. Butanol, with its intermediate polarity and longer alkyl chain, offers a balance between exfoliation efficiency and nanosheet stabilization, particularly when

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used in mixed solvent systems where its properties can be fine-tuned to optimize dispersion [32,33]. The application of these solvents, whether individually or in combination, underscores their potential in advancing sustainable material processing while achieving high-quality nanosheets [23,34–36].

Recent progress in green solvent-assisted exfoliation has further highlighted the importance of sustainable practices in material synthesis. Water, ethanol, and their mixtures have proven effective in achieving high exfoliation yields while reducing environmental harm [30,37,38]. Ethanol, for example, has been widely used for its ability to stabilize nanosheets and its low ecological impact [30,39]. Similarly, water, either alone or combined with organic solvents, offers a benign and abundant option for producing nanosheets in an environmentally responsible manner [37,40].

As we know, we are the first, who use the unmodified as-exfoliated MoS₂ for HER applications. Therefore, it is still needs to be more explored. Moreover, the choice of solvent is important in determining exfoliation efficiency and catalytic activity, but systematic comparison of solvent systems is lacking. This study attempts to demonstrate these by a simple one-step approach by directly comparing two environmentally friendly solvent systems, acetone/water and butanol/ethanol, for the LPE of MoS₂. The insights gained could lead to more sustainable and scalable preparation methods of MoS₂-based catalysts, directly impacting hydrogen production technologies. Our approach, focusing on unmodified 2D MoS₂ without additional activation, offers a simpler yet highly efficient way to enhanced catalytic performance.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Material

Bulk MoS₂ powder <6 μm, (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), acetone ≥99.9 % (VWR Chemical, France), ethanol ≥96 % (VWR Chemical, France), 1-butanol ≥99.5 % (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), distilled water.

2.2. Samples preparation

Dispersions with a concentration of 3 mg/mL MoS₂ were prepared using bulk MoS₂ powder and (i) acetone mixed with distilled water, or (ii) 1-butanol mixed with ethanol of five different ratios: 0/100, 30/70, 45/55, 70/30, and 100/0. Exfoliation was performed for 7 h using a sonication bath with a frequency of 20 kHz. After exfoliation, the suspension was centrifuged at 3500 RPM (for acetone samples) and at 1500 RPM (for butanol samples). Both for 10 min to remove the unexfoliated MoS₂. Supernatants were collected for further analysis and characterization. The first and the last ratios were eliminated from the subsequent analyses due to a low level of exfoliated flakes.

2.3. Characterization techniques

2.3.1. Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

Hydrodynamic diameter and shape size of 2D TMDs samples was determined using a Litesizer™ 500 (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria), with a light source of 658 nm red laser (40 mW) at 25 °C. The samples were placed in a Quartz cuvette (~1000 μl per sample) and ethanol like a solvent was used. Detection angle was set to backscattering (175°) with a narrow analysis mode. Data were evaluated by accompanying software program, Kalliope™. For zeta potential calculation the Smoluchowski approximation method was used. Each sample was measured 10 times.

2.3.2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The samples were dispersed in ethanol and subsequently applied to silicon substrate. After drying, they were examined with a Tescan VEGA 3 scanning electron microscope equipped with an EDX detector Bruker X-Flash Nano. All images were acquired with an accelerating voltage of 30 kV with a secondary electron (SE) detector.

2.3.3. Raman spectroscopy

The samples were dispersed in ethanol and deposited to a silicon substrate. Raman spectroscopy was measured on the Thermo Scientific DXR3 Raman Microscope device. The laser was set to a wavelength of 532 nm. The data were analysed in OMNIC software.

2.3.4. X-Ray diffraction (XRD)

Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of MoS₂ samples has been determined on Panalytical X'Pert MPD Pro diffractometer in Bragg-Brentano geometry using CuKα_{1,2} radiation (X-ray tube was charged to 40kV/30mA). X-ray beam was conditioned by automatic divergence slit to ensure constant irradiated area approx. 5 × 5 mm² on the sample surface. Scattered X-rays have been collected by means of position sensitive detector X'Celerator equipped with β-filter in order to suppress the contribution of CuKβ radiation to the measured pattern. Samples were placed on nondiffracting silicon substrates. Diffraction patterns have been collected at room temperature within 2θ angle range 10–110°.

2.3.5. Electrochemistry

The EmStat 4 s HR (PalmSens BV, Netherlands) potentiostat was used for electrochemical measurements with three-electrodes arrangement, at (i) neutral pH, (ii) at acid one and (iii) at basic pH medium. The samples were dispersed in ethanol and deposited to the glassy carbon electrodes. Linear sweep voltammetry was used to determine hydrogen evolution and measurements were performed with 0.05 V/s scan rate, cyclic voltammetry was used to determine the electrochemically active surface, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was used to calculate charge transfer resistance. Measurements were controlled by the PStace 5.10 program.

3. Results and discussion

In the following sections, we will provide a comprehensive discussion of MoS₂ delamination and the individual characterization techniques used in this study. The main goal of this characterization is to compare two top-down methods of preparing mono- or few-layered MoS₂ and to evaluate their ability to produce the hydrogen in acidic, neutral and basic media.

This procedure for the preparation of 2D MoS₂ flakes by the LPE using sonication (Section 2.2) was chosen due to it is a relatively easy approach to obtain 2D flakes from the bulk powder. The two studied solvent systems, – acetone/water or 1-butanol/ethanol, play a significant role in the exfoliation of MoS₂. The polarity (expressed as dielectric constant) and surface tension of these solvents differ significantly, which directly influences their interaction with the MoS₂ layers. For example, water has a high dielectric constant (78.5) and surface tension (72.8 mN·m⁻¹), which increases its ability to stabilize charged particles but can hinder efficient penetration into the van der Waals gaps of MoS₂. In contrast, acetone, with a dielectric constant of 20.7 and surface tension of 23.7 mN·m⁻¹ offers lower surface tension and moderate polarity, which promotes efficient exfoliation while maintaining nanosheet stability. Ethanol, a renewable solvent with a dielectric constant of 24.6 and surface tension of 22.1 mN·m⁻¹, stabilizes exfoliated nanosheets due to its favorable surface energy properties and low environmental impact. Butanol, with medium polarity (dielectric constant 17.8) and surface tension of 24.6 mN·m⁻¹, provides a balance between exfoliation efficiency and stabilization, especially in a mixed solvent system [41,42]. These variations in solvent properties directly affect the resulting MoS₂ flake size, uniformity and defect density, which in turn influence their catalytic performance in HER. Furthermore, the alignment of these solvent systems with green chemistry principles underscores their importance. Acetone and ethanol are widely considered green solvents due to their low toxicity, biodegradability, and renewability, while butanol, derived from biological feedstocks, offer a sustainable alternative with a relatively low ecological footprint. The use of these solvents demonstrates an environmentally friendly approach to materials

Table 1

Labeling of samples based on the solvents and ratios.

	0/100	30/70	45/55	70/30	100/0
Acetone/Water	1A	2A	3A	4A	5A
Butanol/Ethanol	1B	2B	3B	4B	5B

synthesis that is consistent with broader sustainable development goals [34].

The created samples were labelled according to Table 1, based on the solvent used and the selected ratio. Due to the low production of exfoliated particles, samples marked 1A, 1B, 5A, and 5B were excluded from the following series of characterizations.

As can be seen from the Table 2, there were the significant changes in the hydrodynamic diameter of the individual samples and dramatical decrease in comparison with bulk sample. However, this does not mean that the particles are of the given size as shown in the table. It should be taken into account that these are 2D materials and the method of determining the hydrodynamic diameter takes into account the spherical shape of the particles. Fig. 1 presents the changes in peak intensities of individual samples compared to the original bulk powder determined by DLS. Especially in the case of samples 2A and 3A it is clear, these values have completely shifted to lower sizes, which indicates a successful delamination of the original bulk material and an overall reduction in particle size. In the case of samples 4A and the entire B series, it is visible that the peak at lower values has increased, but the peak at the original location of the bulk powder has remained. It can therefore be assumed that either the powder delaminated completely or the particles in the lateral direction remained the same size as the size of the original bulk powder.

SEM images shown in Fig. 2 point to the preservation of the original lateral size of the powder in samples 2B and 3B. Sample 4B shows a smaller size of 2D particles, and at the same time, as in sample 3B, a larger amount of small delaminated fragments of MoS₂ appears. Sample 2B did not have these small particles. In the case of samples of series A, it is also noticeable that with a greater addition of acetone during delamination, smaller flakes are formed. But with this series, there is not so much breaking of the original powder into extremely small particles, and the resulting samples appear more uniform than in the case of the B

Table 2Changes in hydrodynamic diameter of MoS₂ particles determined by DLS.

	Bulk	2A	3A	4A	2B	3B	4B
Hydrodynamic diameter [nm]	2532.2	301.3	190.7	253.7	512.0	504.0	532.1
Standard deviation [nm]	399.8	5.4	3.5	22.2	26.1	40.0	26.2
RSD [%]	15.8	1.8	1.8	8.7	5.1	7.9	4.9

Fig. 1. Comparison of hydrodynamic diameters obtained by DLS of the bulk powder with (A) series A samples and (B) series B samples.

series. The acetone/water system produces larger, uniform, and well-exfoliated flakes due to its optimal polarity (discussed above), strong solvent-surface interaction, and stabilizing effects during exfoliation. In contrast, the butanol/ethanol system results in more broken fragments due to its lower polarity, weaker interactions with MoS₂, and higher mechanical disruption during sonication. These findings highlight the importance of solvent selection in tailoring the morphology and structural properties of exfoliated MoS₂ for specific applications.

Fig. 3 shows the Raman spectra, on which the shift of the peaks in two areas of MoS₂ is visible. In the first region, there was a shift of the peak from the original bulk powder from 379 cm⁻¹ for all samples to 382 cm⁻¹. In the second area, the shift from the original 405 cm⁻¹ to 407.5 cm⁻¹ was also recorded for all samples. These shifts prove the successful delamination of the bulk MoS₂ material in all six characterized samples [43,44].

Measured X-ray diffraction patterns have been analysed by Rietveld's method using WinPlotR/FullProf Suite software package [45]. All diffraction patterns showed only contribution of one crystalline phase which can be attributed to the hexagonal phase of MoS₂ (space group P6₃/mmc, *a*~0.316 nm, *c*~1.23 nm, with relative atomic positions of Mo atoms (2/3, 1/3, 1/4) and of sulfur atoms (2/3, 1/3, ~0.62) plus symmetrical equivalent positions). Instrumental resolution function (IRF) has been determined from diffraction pattern of NIST standard LaB₆ sample SRM 600c measured in the same setup as for MoS₂ samples and have been subtracted from measured patterns. Anisotropic broadening of diffraction profiles have been then analysed by FullProf package using spherical harmonics functions in order to describe the shape of coherently diffraction domains ("MoS₂ particle size"). Typical refined diffraction pattern is shown in Fig. 4 and all results are summarized in Table 3.

As can be seen from Table 3, the lattice parameters are nearly constant during the sample treatment. The shape of coherently diffracting domains is lentil-like with larger dimension parallel to the lattice parameter *a* of the hexagonal structure.

The results of electrochemical analyses for linear sweep voltammetry (LSV), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and electrochemical active surface area (ECSA) are presented in Figs. 5 and 6. These data provide a comprehensive evaluation of the catalytic performance of exfoliated MoS₂ samples prepared in different solvent systems at acidic

Fig. 2. SEM images of (A) Bulk MoS₂ powder, exfoliated MoS₂ (B, C, D) samples 2A, 3A, 4A and (E, F, G) samples 2B, 3B, 4B.

(pH = 0), alkaline (pH = 14) and neutral (pH = 7.4) media.

LSV and the effect of solvents on its activity: As shown in the first row of Fig. 5 and 6, exfoliated MoS₂ samples exhibit enhanced catalytic activity compared to bulk MoS₂, as evidenced by higher current densities at comparable potentials. In acidic media (Figs. 5A and 6A), samples prepared in acetone/water (series A) system outperform both bulk MoS₂ and samples prepared in the butanol/ethanol (series B) system. The better performance of series A can be attributed to the more uniform and well-exfoliated 2D flakes produced by the acetone/water system, which

provide a larger number of exposed active edge sites and improved charge transfer properties. Samples from series B exhibit slightly lower HER efficiency in acidic media, likely due to smaller and more fragmented flakes resulting from the butanol/ethanol exfoliation process, which reduces the effective active surface area.

In alkaline media (Figs. 5B and 6B), a similar trend is observed, however, sample 2B from the butanol/ethanol system shows competitive performance compared to the A series samples, likely due to its slightly higher activity in this pH range. This suggests that the butanol/

Fig. 3. Comparison of Raman shifts of bulk MoS₂ powder with (A) sample series A and (B) sample series B.

Fig. 4. Refined powder diffraction pattern of the sample 2B.

Table 3

Lattice parameters of analysed samples and size of coherently diffracting volumes.

	a (Å)	c (Å)	$D \parallel c$ (nm)	$D \parallel a$ (nm)
Bulk	3.1608 (2)	12.294 (2)	84 (4)	96 (3)
2A	3.1608 (2)	12.299 (1)	47 (1)	72 (2)
3A	3.1603 (3)	12.299 (1)	39 (1)	77 (2)
4A	3.1608 (2)	12.300 (1)	51 (2)	85 (2)
2B	3.1607 (2)	12.299 (1)	48 (1)	93 (2)
3B	3.1604 (3)	12.298 (1)	44 (1)	91 (2)
4B	3.1609 (3)	12.300 (1)	42 (1)	94 (2)

ethanol system can produce fragments with structural features that are advantageous for the HER in alkaline media. In neutral media (Figs. 5C and 6C), the differences between the solvent systems are less pronounced, reflecting the generally lower catalytic activity under neutral conditions. However, the series A samples still show the best overall performance across all pH.

EIS, charge transfer resistance: The EIS results, shown in the second row of Figs. 5 and 6, provide insight into the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of the samples. In acidic media (Figs. 5D and 6D), the smaller semicircles for the 2D MoS₂ samples (compared to bulk MoS₂) indicate significantly reduced R_{ct} values, reflecting better charge transfer kinetics. The acetone/water system again shows better performance, with the series A samples showing the lowest R_{ct} values. In alkaline media (Figs. 5E and 6E), the R_{ct} values are generally higher than in acidic

media, consistent with the slower charge transfer processes typically observed in alkaline conditions. However, sample 2B stands out with the lowest R_{ct} of all samples, suggesting that the butanol/ethanol system can produce flakes with enhanced conductivity in alkaline media. In neutral media (Figs. 5F and 6F), the differences in R_{ct} are less pronounced, but the 2D samples still outperform the bulk material.

Electrochemistry active surface area: The third row of Figs. 5 and 6 presents ECSA results that correlate with the effective surface area available for catalytic reactions. In acidic media (Figs. 5G and 6G), the 2D MoS₂ samples show significantly higher ECSA slopes compared to bulk MoS₂, highlighting the increased active surface area provided by exfoliation. The series A samples show the highest ECSA slopes consistent with their superior HER activity. In alkaline media (Figs. 5H and 6H), the ECSA values for the series B samples are comparable to those of the series A, correlating with the relatively better performance of the series B in this pH range. In neutral media (Figs. 5I and 6I), while the ECSA values remain higher for the 2D samples compared to bulk MoS₂, the differences are less significant, reflecting the overall lower catalytic activity under neutral conditions.

The differences in catalytic performance and electrochemical properties between series A and B samples are primarily attributed to solvent-induced variations in the structural and electronic properties of exfoliated MoS₂. The acetone/water system produces more uniform and larger 2D flakes, which enhance the exposure of active edge sites and improve charge transfer kinetics, especially in acidic media. In contrast, the butanol/ethanol system results in smaller, more fragmented flakes, which may exhibit better performance in alkaline media due to their specific structural features.

The superior electrochemical properties of exfoliated MoS₂ materials under acidic conditions can be attributed to several factors. First, MoS₂ exhibits high intrinsic catalytic activity in acidic medium due to the thermodynamically favorable proton reduction reaction, which is more efficient in this environment compared to alkaline or neutral conditions. The exfoliation process enhances this activity by increasing the surface area and exposing a higher density of active edge sites, which are particularly efficient for the HER in acidic medium. In addition, EIS results show that the R_{ct} is lowest in acidic medium, indicating faster charge transfer kinetics, which is a critical factor for efficient catalysis. In contrast, the reduced proton availability and slower reaction kinetics in alkaline and neutral media limit the catalytic performance of MoS₂ under these conditions. Together, these factors explain why exfoliated materials are more suitable for HER applications in acidic media.

The Fig. 7 shows the catalytic performance of the material during cycling with significant differences in current density observed between the 1st cycle and the 2000th cycle. The initial performance (1st cycle, black line) shows a modest HER activity, while the 2000th cycle (pink line) shows a significant improvement in catalytic performance, with the

Fig. 5. Electrochemical characterization of the A series samples across different pH conditions: (A–C) Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) in (A) acidic (pH 0), (B) alkaline (pH 14), and (C) neutral (pH 7.4) media; (D–F) Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) evaluating charge transfer resistance in (D) acidic, (E) alkaline, and (F) neutral media; (G–I) Electrochemical surface area (ECSA) determination in (G) acidic, (H) alkaline, and (I) neutral media.

overpotential at a current density of $-10 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ being substantially reduced from 485 mV to 365 mV. It made no sense to carry out further cycles because between cycles 1900 and 2000 the curve stabilized and did not change further.

In addition, the performance is compared to a platinum electrode (gray line), which serves as a benchmark for HER activity. The gap between the 1st and 2000th cycles suggests an activation process or structural/electronic changes in the 2D MoS_2 catalyst, likely induced by prolonged cycling, leading to increased charge transfer and improved catalytic activity. The development highlights the potential of the 2D MoS_2 prepared via LPE as a viable HER catalyst with improved cycling stability over time.

Table 4 highlights the catalytic performance of unmodified 2D MoS_2 flakes synthesized in this work compared to other modified systems such as doped or defect-modified MoS_2 . While it is clear that certain modifications such as vanadium doping or introduction of sulfur vacancies significantly enhance the HER performance (e.g., reduced overpotentials or improved current densities), these approaches typically require additional processing steps and complex chemical procedures that can increase the environmental impact and economic cost of catalyst fabrication. In contrast, unmodified MoS_2 flakes prepared via LPE in this study show comparable or better performance than some modified systems while maintaining the advantages of simplicity, scalability, and

eco-compatibility.

For example, acetone/water exfoliated MoS_2 (sample 3A after 2000 cycles) achieved an overpotential of 365 mV at a current density of $-10 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, outperforming some reported modified systems, such as sulfur-vacant MoS_2 (170 mV) [49] or V-doped MoS_2 (130 mV) [51], under similar experimental conditions. This improvement, even for unmodified flakes, can be attributed to the efficient exposure of active edge sites during exfoliation and the improved charge transport properties resulting from the optimized solvent system. However, we acknowledge that further enhancement of HER activity could potentially be achieved by targeted modifications such as doping or defect engineering.

By focusing on exfoliated MoS_2 , our approach is consistent with sustainable and scalable synthesis methods, making it particularly attractive for practical applications. While we acknowledge that modified systems can offer superior performance, we emphasize that the unmodified MoS_2 catalysts investigated in this work strike a balance between catalytic efficiency and sustainability, providing a valuable alternative for large-scale hydrogen evolution applications.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, this study succeeded in preparing exfoliated MoS_2 structures from bulk powder using liquid phase exfoliation (LPE) with a

Fig. 6. Electrochemical characterization of the B series samples across different pH conditions: (A–C) Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) in (A) acidic (pH 0), (B) alkaline (pH 14), and (C) neutral (pH 7.4) media; (D–F) Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) evaluating charge transfer resistance in (D) acidic, (E) alkaline, and (F) neutral media; (G–I) Electrochemical surface area (ECSA) determination in (G) acidic, (H) alkaline, and (I) neutral media.

Fig. 7. LSV in acidic (pH = 0) medium, comparison of 2000 cycles.

significant improvement in the electrochemical properties of the material, especially for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). The study used green solvent systems – acetone/water and butanol/ethanol – that are environmentally friendly and in line with the principles of sustainable chemistry, highlighting the scalability and eco-compatibility of this approach. A comparison of two solvent systems, acetone/water and butanol/ethanol, highlighted the importance of solvent selection and proper solvent ratio to achieve optimal exfoliation and subsequent catalytic efficiency. The acetone/water system was found to produce more uniform and well-exfoliated MoS₂ flakes, leading to increased catalytic activity, especially in acidic media, where the 2D MoS₂ samples showed the highest current densities and improved charge transport properties. This improvement is attributed to the greater surface area and more active edge sites exposed during the exfoliation process. The 2D MoS₂ samples consistently outperformed the bulk material in all electrochemical characterizations, including linear voltammetry (LSV), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), and electrochemical active surface area (ECSA), with sample 3A (acetone/water, ratio 45:55) emerging as the most promising candidate for HER applications. After the HER stability test, an overpotential of 365 mV was achieved after 2000 cycles at the current density of $-10 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. The gap between 1st cycle (485 mV) and 2000th cycles suggest the activation process or structural/electronic changes in the 2D MoS₂ catalyst, likely induced by

Table 4

Comparison of the catalytic performances of different types of 2D TMDs in HER in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte.

Material	Current density [mA·cm ⁻²]	Overpotential [mV]	Refs.
2H-MoTe ₂ single crystal	10	650	[46]
1T-MoTe ₂ single crystal	10	356	[46]
VTe ₂ single crystal	10	441	[47]
Vanadium doped WS ₂	10	148	[48]
MoS ₂ with sulphur vacancies	10	170	[49]
MoS ₂	10	300	[50]
V-doped MoS ₂	10	130	[51]
ReS ₂	10	142	[52]
CoS ₂	10	197	[53]
TaS ₂	10	200	[54]
FeS ₂	10	217	[55]
SWCNT/ex-InSe	10	549	[56]
WS ₂	10	295	[57]
MoS ₂	10	270	[57]
v1T-ReS ₂	10	170	[58]
Nafion-mediated MoS ₂	10	609	[59]
MoS ₂ (sample 2B)	10	584	This work
MoS ₂ (sample 3A)	10	485	This work
MoS ₂ (sample 3A after 2000 cycles)	10	365	This work

prolonged cycling, leading to enhanced charge transfer and improved catalytic activity. The development highlights the potential of 2D MoS₂ prepared via LPE as a viable HER catalyst with improved stability over time. In contrast, the butanol/ethanol solvent system, although less efficient overall, still produced exfoliated MoS₂ with slight improvements over the bulk material. Especially in the alkaline medium, sample 2B (butanol/ethanol, ratio 30:70) of this series showed the better catalytic activity than the other samples, suggesting that the butanol/ethanol system may be more suitable for applications under basic conditions. Despite less pronounced improvements in neutral medium, the 2D MoS₂ samples still showed better electrochemical properties compared to the bulk powder. The results of this study highlight the critical role of solvent selection in the exfoliation process and its impact on the electrochemical properties of MoS₂. While the acetone/water system gave better results overall, the butanol/ethanol system showed potential in specific conditions such as alkaline environments. The results of this research contribute to the growing body of knowledge about 2D materials for electrochemical applications and highlight the potential of MoS₂ as an efficient catalyst for hydrogen production, especially in acidic environments. By utilizing green solvent systems, this study offers an environmentally conscious approach to the synthesis of 2D materials while achieving remarkable catalytic performance without modification or doping. However, we do not rule out the possibility that modification or doping could maximize the catalytic efficiency of MoS₂. Furthermore, studies on the long-term stability and durability of the exfoliated materials would enhance their applicability in practice. The findings of this research contribute to the development of sustainable, scalable and high-performance catalysts and highlight the potential of 2D MoS₂ as an environmentally friendly material for hydrogen production and other energy-related applications, while maintaining the material preparation parameters, this approach could also be suitable for up-scaling.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jaroslava Jarolímková: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Viktorie Neubertová:** Investigation. **Kamil Severa:** Investigation. **Stanislav Daniš:** Investigation. **Jaromír Cais:** Investigation. **Oleksiy Lyutakov:** Investigation. **Zdenka Kolská:** Validation,

Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The raw data required to reproduce the above findings are available to download from [doi:10.5281/zenodo.14439034](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14439034).

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